

ETHICAL PRINCIPLES IN THE MEDIA ENVIRONMENT

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Abstract: This article is full of interesting information about ethical principles in the media environment, correct use of the Internet, media, media types, and soon.

Key words: moral principles, behavior, media space, internet

Any society has its own moral rules, and each person lives according to his inner convictions. Along with moral principles, high moral principles should also be emphasized. High moral principles are a moral standard of behavior, thinking, worldview that every person should strive for. Moral foundations play a very important role in the life of any person, because thanks to them, human society exists and continues to develop. They allow you to be intelligent and not fall to the level of an animal with only instincts. It should be remembered that a person always remains a person, regardless of family, enemies, friends or at work, and not only not to violate personal moral principles, but also to overcome negative emotions, fear, should try to overcome the pain. Each socially formed person has its own moral foundations. Thus, everyone has moral and ethical principles that he follows in his daily life. This article is about what ethics is. How does it develop in the human mind and how is it reflected in everyday life? To begin with, it is necessary to give the concept of what is moral or, also, moral basis. Moral basis is the moral basis of every individual or social group. The formation of such foundations takes place under the influence of any spiritual doctrine, religion, upbringing, education or state propaganda and culture.

Moral foundations, as a rule, are subject to change, and this is a change in worldview during life, and sometimes things that once seemed to be the norm turn into unacceptable situations over time, or vice versa. In addition to moral principles, it is necessary to emphasize high moral principles. Information is a means of managing a person, his actions, activities of public organizations, state authorities, and technical systems. Communication of information forms the basis of upbringing, education and formation of a person. Information is the only means of conveying to a person the content of social and technical norms, warning him about the future negative consequences of not following these norms. we observe current topics, events, and events happening in the world through the first mass media. In this regard, principles such as promptness,

objectivity, accuracy are of primary importance to the audience. Nowadays, the Internet has become an integral part of our life as a space for receiving and distributing information. The global network, globalization has also fundamentally changed the concept of information and mass media. Today, Internet journalism, which is developing further and acquiring new directions, is distinguished by its comprehensiveness and the fact that its audience knows no boundaries. Internet journalism, which is considered a type of modern mass media. Development of mass media, expansion of its tasks, sharp changes in the field of production and technology, complication of relations between journalism and society, put new tasks in front of journalists. Nowadays, it is important to train universal journalists who can simultaneously write news, acquire the skills of interviewing, taking photos and videos, and prepare materials for the Internet. At the same time, these traditional journalistic skills are now being supplemented with technical skills in areas such as mathematics and engineering. This is especially important for journalists who use the Internet. Thus, the convergence of different fields requires both universalization and specialization from journalists. At the same time, universalization, or rather, transprofessionalization, first of all, requires complete mastery of one area. A universal journalist means a specialist who has completely mastered a specific field. The Internet is the only popular computer network that is in demand today, and it is a source of information that provides us with open, simple and fluent information about the uncertainty in all areas, that is, the concepts that are abstract to our minds. Of course, the number of people who need this factor is increasing day by day. This network is a global network worldwide. Because there are news reports, image and sound services and a number of opportunities that create great relief on all fronts, but on the other hand, they are involuntarily attracting people to the virtual world. Especially teenagers are not absent from this sphere of influence. In this regard, the words of experts prove the following results:

It is obvious that the positivity of the Internet leads to the all-round convenience of a person in having important concrete evidence related to science, field and activity, and the saving of the corresponding amount of time, but due to curiosity, they are overly addicted to excessive information on the Internet. Inquisitiveness, mental development, observation, analytical ability and memory acuity decrease.

It is known that the use of the Internet tool is not obligatory for anyone, and it should be based on the law and the rules of the person's own thinking, as well as

the standard requirements, that is, the correct selection of information from the Internet network. is appropriate. It can be seen that the scale of information contained in this network tool is so wide and numerous that it sometimes makes it difficult for us to extract the information we need. Media ethics is the subdivision dealing with the specific ethical principles and standards of media, including broadcast media, film, theatre, the arts, print media and the internet. The field covers many varied and highly controversial topics, ranging from war journalism to Benetton ad campaigns. Media ethics promotes and defends values such as a universal respect for life and the rule of law and legality. Media Ethics defines and deals with ethical questions about how media should use texts and pictures provided by the citizens.

Literature regarding the ways in which specifically the Internet impacts media ethics in journalism online is scarce, thereby complicating the idea for a universal code of media ethics. Media ethics is a branch of ethics that addresses moral issues arising in connection with the acquisition, preparation, storage, presentation, dissemination, and reception of information through the means of mass media. Mass media include print media (newspapers, magazines, and books), recordings, motion pictures, and electronic media (radio, television, and the computer). Media ethics seeks to help the media practitioners resolve various moral problems arising in all the areas of media communications: journalism, advertising, public relations, and entertainment. The media exercise a strong and complex influence upon the perception and understanding of the world by the public and, consequently, upon shaping the personality of each individual and the interactions of individuals with one another. News and reportage, commercials and advertisements, soap operas, and films – all exert in the long run more or less subtle influence on people's views, choices, and behavior. Because of the ubiquity of the media and their growing presence, the ethical problems that the media practitioners face become increasingly important. The number of publications and conferences on media indicates that among the issues that concern the media people and the public the most important are truth in the media (objectivity and fairness), freedom and responsibility (self-regulatory mechanisms), privacy, and the quality of the media content .

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